

Surgical techniques for uterine closure in caesarean section

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Background

Description of the condition

Caesarean sections (CSs) are the most frequently performed major abdominal surgeries in the world [1] and this mode of delivery has steadily increased since the 1990s. Current global estimates indicate that approximately 21% of all births occur via CS, and this may rise to 30% by 2030 [2]. Despite substantial variations in CS rates within and between different countries [3], in several middle-income countries — including the Dominican Republic, Brazil, Egypt and Turkey — over 50% of women currently give birth by CS [2].

As with any surgery, a CS carries inherent risks associated with anesthesia, the operation itself, and the postoperative period. Compared to vaginal births, CSs are associated with increased risks of short- and long-term maternal complications such as postpartum hemorrhage, infectious morbidity, abdominal adhesions, and higher risks of uterine rupture and placenta previa and accreta in subsequent pregnancies [4, 5, 6]. Delivery by CS also exposes the offspring to risks such as neonatal respiratory disorders, as well as obesity and asthma later in life [5, 6, 7]. Maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality associated with CS are higher in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC), where surgical safety and access to quality care may be limited [8]. This is especially relevant because it is estimated that 88% of the 38 million CSs projected for 2030 will occur in LMIC [2].

Despite being a very common operation, there are wide variations in CS techniques and practices within and between different settings and regions [9, 10, 11, 12, 13], and conflicting local guidelines. This lack of standardization may be exacerbated by the lack of clear and comprehensive internationally accepted guidelines and recommendations.

Description of the intervention and how it might work

The many surgical procedures involved in a CS can be grouped into three main phases: a) opening of the abdominal wall; b) uterine incision, delivery of the baby/placenta, and uterine suture; and c) closure of the abdominal wall.

For closure of the uterine wall, a variety of suture materials and techniques may be used, and the uterus can be repaired either inside or outside the abdominal cavity. [16] Suture

materials include multifilament versus monofilament, barbed versus non-barbed, and chromic catgut versus polyglactin 910 sutures. Suturing techniques may involve single-layer versus double-layer closure, interrupted versus continuous sutures, and locked versus unlocked sutures. [15]

Extra-abdominal uterine closure may improve visualisation of the incision site and provide more space for suturing, potentially reducing intraoperative bleeding. However, removal of the uterus from the abdominal cavity and traction on the uterine ligaments may cause a drop in blood pressure, an increase in nausea and vomiting, and post-op pain. It may also affect the risk of infection. The choice of suture material and technique may also influence blood loss and infection risk, as well as the development of uterine scar defects with associated problems like uterine rupture or scar dehiscence in subsequent pregnancies.

Understanding the best evidence for closing the uterus during CS is therefore crucial to ensure maternal safety and long-term reproductive health.

Why it is important to do this review

Despite being one of the most commonly performed surgeries conducted worldwide, currently, there are no universally accepted, evidence-based guidelines about the procedures involved in closing the uterus. Existing recommendations are often fragmented and, in some cases, contradictory, contributing to inconsistency in clinical practice and uncertainty among providers. As a result, more effective and safer procedures may be underutilized, while less optimal procedures may continue to be widely used, potentially exposing women to unnecessary risks.

In the absence of internationally recognized recommendations, the choice of technique and materials used is influenced by many factors, including the patient's clinical situation, the costs of suture material, and the surgeon's preferences, beliefs, or previous experience.

Previous Cochrane systematic reviews have addressed several procedures used in incising and closing the uterus. [[14](#), [15](#), [16](#)] However, these reviews are outdated, and several new trials have been conducted since their publication, warranting an updated systematic review. To support the development of World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines on surgical techniques for CS, the questions and specific comparisons from previous reviews

were regrouped, and this review will assess uterine closure procedures (including extra- and intra-abdominal closure) only. Uterine incision procedures will be assessed in another independent review.

The evidence identified in this review is expected to reduce inter-surgeon variability, ensure that best practices are followed, and improve the quality of care and outcomes for millions of women worldwide. With the rising CS rates, it becomes increasingly important to adopt evidence-based operative procedures to optimize patient outcomes and to contribute to more efficient use of resources—particularly in health systems that are already strained and resource-limited.

Objectives

The main objective of this systematic review is to assess the benefits and harms of different surgical techniques used to close the uterus in women undergoing a CS.

The specific questions are:

- For women undergoing a caesarean section (P), does extra-abdominal closure of the uterus (I) compared to intra-abdominal closure of the uterus (C), improve maternal outcomes (O)?
- For women undergoing a caesarean section (P) does any particular suture material (I) compared with alternative suture material (C) improve maternal outcomes (O)?
- For women undergoing caesarean section (P), does any particular suturing technique (I) compared with an alternative suturing technique (C) improve maternal outcomes (O)?

Methods

We will follow the Methodological expectations for Cochrane intervention reviews (MECIR) when conducting the review [17], and PRISMA 2020 for the reporting [18].

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

All randomised controlled trials (RCTs) or cluster-randomised trials comparing the effectiveness and safety of a single specific procedure to alternative procedures for closing

the uterus in a CS will be eligible for inclusion. Quasi- randomised trials will be excluded.

Types of participants

The review will include RCTs that recruited pregnant women (general obstetric population), of any parity, with or without a previous CS, giving birth by CS at term (≥ 37 weeks gestational age). Trials that only included women with specific underlying medical or obstetric conditions that may require specialized interventions (e.g. women with morbid obesity, uterine anomalies, multiple repeat CS, or placenta previa), will not be considered in this SR. Trials including only a subset of eligible participants will be included if the majority of participants are eligible for inclusion.

Types of interventions

The surgical procedures involved in closing the uterus include the use of different techniques and materials.

Trials will be eligible if they tested a single specific procedure compared to a different procedure for uterine closure. Procedures will be grouped into the following three comparisons:

- Extra-abdominal vs intra-abdominal uterine closure
- One type of suture material compared to a different type of suture material (i.e. different types of needles, different sutures)
- One suturing technique or combination of techniques compared to a different suturing technique or combination of techniques (techniques include single layer vs. two layers, interrupted vs. continuous sutures, locked vs. unlocked sutures).

This systematic review will not include suturing of the visceral peritoneum nor uterine closure techniques as part of complete caesarean section techniques. These procedures will be assessed in other independent reviews.

Outcome measures

There are no core outcome sets for the surgical aspects of a CS. An initial list of outcomes was created based on a recent overview of systematic reviews on surgical interventions in CS [19], the Coronis trial [20], other reviews and international guidelines [21, 22, 23, 24, 25,

[26](#)], and the experience of international health experts obtained through informal consultations.

Through author team discussions and input from WHO, we divided the outcomes pertinent to uterine closure into critical, important and secondary outcomes as reported below. However, the importance rating of the outcomes by the guideline development group (GDG), convened by the WHO, is ongoing, and we will review these outcomes once the rating results are available. Outcome definitions are reported in Table 1.

Critical outcomes

Extra-abdominal vs intra-abdominal uterine closure

1. Intra-operative pain
2. Intra-operative nausea or vomiting

One type of suture material compared to a different type of suture material

1. Uterine scar defect (Niche) in subsequent pregnancy
2. Abdominal adhesions in subsequent pregnancy

One suturing technique or combination of techniques compared to a different suturing technique or combination of techniques

1. Uterine scar defect (Niche) in subsequent pregnancy
2. Uterine scar dehiscence in subsequent pregnancy

Important outcomes

Extra-adominal vs intra-abdominal uterine closure

1. Post-partum haemorrhage (PPH)
2. Total operative time
3. Infectious morbidity
4. Severe morbidity
5. Post-operative pain

One type of suture material compared to a different type of suture material

1. Placental anomalies in subsequent pregnancy
2. Uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancy

3. Uterine scar dehiscence in subsequent pregnancy
4. Infectious morbidity
5. Severe morbidity

One suturing technique or combination of techniques compared to a different suturing technique or combination of techniques

1. Uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancy
2. Placental anomalies in subsequent pregnancy
3. Total operative time
4. Post-partum haemorrhage (PPH)
5. Severe morbidity

Secondary outcomes

We will extract these outcomes if they are available and report them in supplementary material. However, we will not assess risk of bias for these outcomes, and they will not be reported in the Summary of Findings tables.

Extra-abdominal vs intra-abdominal uterine closure

- Length of hospital stay
- Surgical site infection
- Endometritis
- Sepsis
- Febrile morbidity
- Blood loss
- Blood transfusion
- Need for additional uterotonics
- Maternal death
- Post-operative nausea or vomiting
- Time to bowel movement

One type of suture material compared to a different type of suture material

- Total operative time
- Length of hospital stay

- Intra-operative pain
- Post-operative pain
- Chronic pelvic pain
- Surgical site infection
- Endometritis
- Sepsis
- Febrile morbidity
- Blood loss
- Post-partum haemorrhage (PPH)
- Blood transfusion
- Need for additional uterotonics
- Maternal death

One suturing technique or combination of techniques compared to a different suturing technique or combination of techniques

- Length of hospital stay
- Intra-operative pain
- Post-operative pain
- Chronic pelvic pain
- Surgical site infection
- Endometritis
- Sepsis
- Febrile morbidity
- Blood loss
- Blood transfusion
- Need for additional uterotonics
- Maternal death
- Abdominal adhesions
- Dysmenorrhea

Search methods for identification of studies

Electronic searches

Working in collaboration with Cochrane Central's information specialists, we will search MEDLINE, Cochrane Library, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, CINAHL, and Open Alex using a preliminary search strategy in MEDLINE (Supplementary material) that will be adapted to other electronic databases.

In addition, we will search the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) and the US National Library of Medicine for unpublished, planned and ongoing trial reports.

If papers are not accessible, we will contact relevant authors and organizations.

Searches will be updated prior to finalising the analysis. Further studies identified and included at this point will be integrated into the final analysis.

Searching other resources

We will retrieve additional relevant references cited in papers identified through the above search strategy and will search for the full texts of trials initially identified as abstracts. We will also hand search references of systematic reviews of eligible studies published in the last 5 years. We will not apply any language or date restrictions. We will contact experts in the field to ensure that we did not miss any unpublished or ongoing trials with our search. Before the review publication, we will search the Retraction Watch Database to look for possible retractions of included studies. We will also search MEDLINE for possible post-publication amendments of included studies.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two review authors will independently and in duplicate assess the titles, abstracts, and full texts of all the potential studies identified for inclusion. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion or, if required, in consultation with a third author. We will use Covidence software [27] to screen references.

Screening eligible studies for scientific integrity/trustworthiness

All studies meeting our inclusion criteria will also be evaluated against predefined criteria to select studies that, based on available information, were deemed to be sufficiently trustworthy to be included in the analysis. We will use the INSPECT-SR tool (INVeStigating ProblEmatic Clinical Trials in Systematic Reviews), a tool created by an international group of researchers to address the risks posed by untrustworthy RCTs [28]. This tool guides reviewers through 21 structured checks across four domains Table 2:

- post-publication notices (3 checks)
- study conduct, governance and transparency (5 checks)
- texts and figures (2 checks)
- study results (11 checks)

Each check consists of a yes/no question and a “yes” answer indicates a potential problem. After completing all checks in a domain, an overall judgement (no concerns”, “some concerns”, or “serious concerns”) will be made regarding the trustworthiness of the study for that domain (Figure 1). After completing judgments for each domain, an overall study-level judgment will be made. The overall judgment should be at least as severe as the most severe domain-level judgment. An overall study-level judgment of “serious concerns” may be appropriate if several domains have “some concerns”. Clear justifications for each domain-level and study-level judgment will be provided.

Two authors will independently and in duplicate assess trustworthiness of all eligible studies. Discrepancies will be resolved through discussions with the rest of the author team. Where we have insufficient information to make a judgement, we will contact study authors and place the study in "awaiting classification" until we have sufficient information to substantiate our trustworthiness assessment. Studies classified as having “serious concerns” at the overall study-level will be excluded from the systematic review analyses. We will restrict our primary analysis to studies with 'no concerns', however, studies with 'some concerns' will be included in a sensitivity analysis.

Data extraction and management

Electronic forms, developed in Covidence [27], will be used to extract data. For eligible studies, at least two review authors will independently extract the data using a blank

electronic form. Discrepancies will be resolved through discussion or, if required, consultation with another person. When information is unclear, we will attempt to contact authors of the original reports to provide further details.

From each included study, we will extract the following:

- **Study methods:** study design, number of intervention arms, start and end dates, time of follow-up, etc.
- **Population:** inclusion and exclusion criteria, number of participants, age, sex, gender, ethnicity, and socio-economic status
- **Potential effect modifiers**
 - moment of CS (pre-labor or intrapartum)
 - type of CS (primary or repeat)
 - type of anaesthesia (regional vs general)
- **Interventions and comparisons:** comparisons and all relevant arm level data (e.g. number of events and number of patients for binary outcomes and means and standard deviations per study arm for continuous outcomes)
- **Outcomes:** primary and secondary outcomes
- **Additional information**
 - country or countries in which the study was performed (location)
 - type of hospital (tertiary, teaching, other)
 - type of provider conducting the CS (resident, OBGYN, surgeon, other)
 - date of publication and dates of recruitment
 - type of publication (full-text publication, unpublished data)
 - trial registration reference
 - funding sources
 - conflicts of interest
 - ethics approval
 - whether authors were contacted for information or not

Risk of bias assessment in included studies

Two reviewers will independently and in duplicate assess the risk of bias of included RCTs using the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool 2: RoB 2.0 [29]. We will resolve any disagreement by discussion or by involving a third assessor.

For each included trial and each critical and important outcome, we will assess the following domains of bias:

(1a) Bias arising from the randomisation process.

(1b) (For cluster trials only [30]) Bias arising from identification or recruitment of individual participants within clusters.

(2) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

(3) Bias due to missing outcome data

(4) Bias in measurement of the outcome

(5) Bias in selection of the reported result

For each domain of bias above, we will provide an explicit assessment of whether there is low risk, some concerns, or high risk of bias, and make a judgement about overall risk of bias (low risk, some concerns, high risk) for a specific outcome according to the pre-specified algorithm. [31].

Measures of treatment effect

Dichotomous data

For dichotomous data, we will present results as a summary risk ratio (RR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Continuous data

For continuous data, we will use the mean difference (MD) with 95% CI if the outcomes are measured in the same way across trials. We will use the standardised mean difference (SMD) to combine data from trials that measure the same outcome, but use different methods.

Thresholds

We will not use any prespecified thresholds to interpret the size of effect.

Unit of analysis issues

Cluster-randomized trials

We will include cluster-randomized trials in the analyses along with individually randomized trials. We will adjust their sample sizes using the methods described in the Cochrane

Handbook [32], using an estimate of the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) derived from the trial (if possible), from a similar trial, or from a study of a similar population. If we use ICCs from other sources, we will report this and conduct sensitivity analyses to investigate the effect of variation in the ICC. If we identify both cluster-randomized trials and individually randomized trials, we plan to synthesize the relevant information.

We will consider it reasonable to combine the results from both cluster-randomized trials and individually randomized trials if there is little heterogeneity between the study designs and the interaction between the effect of intervention and the choice of randomization unit is considered to be unlikely. We will also acknowledge heterogeneity in the randomization unit and perform a sensitivity analysis to investigate the effects of the randomization unit.

Multiple intervention groups

For multiple intervention groups, we will combine the relevant intervention groups into a single intervention group and the relevant control intervention groups into a single control group.

Factorial designs

For factorial designs, we will combine participants who received the relevant intervention into the intervention group and participants who did not receive the relevant intervention into the control group.

Dealing with missing data

For included studies, we will note levels of attrition. For all outcomes, we will carry out analyses on an intention-to-treat basis as far as possible, i.e. we will attempt to include all participants randomized to each group in the analyses, and all participants will be analyzed in the group to which they were allocated, regardless of whether or not they received the allocated intervention. The denominator for each outcome in each trial will be the number randomized minus any participants whose outcomes are known to be missing.

Reporting bias assessment

If there are 10 or more studies in the meta-analysis, we will investigate reporting biases (such as publication bias) using funnel plots. We will assess funnel plot asymmetry visually. If asymmetry is suggested by a visual assessment, we will perform exploratory analyses to

investigate it.

For continuous outcomes, we will use the test proposed by Egger 1997 [33] and for dichotomous outcomes we will use the test proposed by Harbord 2006 [34]. If asymmetry is detected in any of these tests or is suggested by a visual assessment, we will perform exploratory analyses to investigate it.

Synthesis methods

We will perform standard pairwise meta-analyses using an inverse variance random-effects model for every procedure comparison with at least two trials, using Review Manager software (Review Manager Web (RevMan Web). Version (7.3.0) 2024). The random-effects method is preferred as it incorporates an assumption that the different studies are estimating different, yet related, intervention effects [35]. We will use the Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) method to estimate heterogeneity variance (Tau^2). In analyses of two or more studies, where Tau^2 is greater than zero, we will use the Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman (HKSJ) method to calculate 95%CI for the summary effect. In cases where the analysis is limited to two studies, or where Tau^2 is equal to zero, we will calculate the 95%CI for the summary effect using the Wald-type method.

Investigation of heterogeneity and subgroup analysis

We will assess statistical heterogeneity in each meta-analysis using the Tau^2 , I^2 and Chi^2 statistics. We will regard heterogeneity as substantial if I^2 is greater than 30% and either Tau^2 is greater than zero, or there is a low P value (less than 0.10) in the Chi^2 test for heterogeneity.

If we identify substantial heterogeneity, we will investigate it using subgroup analyses.

We plan to carry out the following subgroup analyses for all the important and critical outcomes:

- Moment of CS (pre-labor or intrapartum)
- Type of CS (primary or repeat)
- Type of anaesthesia (regional vs general)

We will consider the P-value of the Chi^2 test and the I^2 statistic to examine differences between subgroups.

Sensitivity analysis

We will conduct sensitivity analyses to explore the effect of trial 'trustworthiness' for each comparison by including trials judged to have 'some concerns' according to the INSPECT-SR tool.

We will conduct sensitivity analyses to explore the effect of trial quality for each comparison by restricting the analysis to those trials rated as 'low risk of bias' for random sequence generation and allocation concealment.

For each comparison, we will limit analyses to the critical and important outcomes.

Certainty of the evidence assessment

The certainty of the overall evidence will be assessed using the GRADE approach, as outlined in the GRADE handbook, to assess the certainty of the body of evidence relating to the primary outcomes [36].

The final list of important and critical outcomes will be presented in the Summary of Findings (SoF) table.

We will import data from RevMan to the GRADEpro Guideline Development Tool [37] to create 'Summary of findings' tables. A summary of the intervention effect and a measure of certainty for each of the primary outcomes will be produced using the GRADE approach. The GRADE approach uses five considerations (consistency of effect, imprecision, indirectness, publication bias, and overall risk of bias) to assess the certainty of the body of evidence for each outcome. The evidence can be downgraded from 'high certainty' by one level for serious (or by two levels for very serious) limitations, depending on assessments for risk of bias, indirectness of evidence, serious inconsistency, imprecision of effect estimates or potential publication bias.

For imprecision, we will downgrade if there are very few events (fewer than 30) or if the CI is very wide. Using a threshold of 0.75 for the relative effect of appreciable benefit and 1.25 for appreciable harm, we will downgrade by one, two, or three levels depending on whether the CI crosses these thresholds.

Two review authors will independently appraise certainty ratings. Disagreements between authors will be resolved through discussion and consultation with a third review author

where necessary. The quality of evidence for each outcome will be rated as ‘high’, ‘moderate’, ‘low’ or ‘very low’, in accordance with the GRADE approach and explained below.

- High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the effect.
- Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.
- Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Equity considerations

We will collect data on age, sex, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status and location of trial participants to report which populations the evidence truly represents and to discuss potential gaps in the applicability of the review findings.

Consumer involvement

We will not involve consumers due to limited resources; however, the review is commissioned by the WHO to inform guidelines on CS, and the evidence from this review will be interpreted by the GDG, which consists of diverse interest-holders, in making recommendations. The GDG also identified outcomes to consider in the review and will rate the importance of these outcomes, ensuring decisions are based on patient-important outcomes.

Additional information

Acknowledgements

Not applicable

Contributions of authors

All authors prepared the protocol draft and read and approved the final version.

Declarations of interest

GJH is conducting a trial that may be eligible for inclusion in a future update of this review. He will not participate in any decisions regarding that trial. SSvW, ET, MRT and AR: No commercial or non-commercial conflicts of interest relevant to this review.

Sources of support

Internal sources

- New Source of support, Other None

External sources

- WHO, Other

SvW received financial support from the WHO to complete this protocol.

Registration and protocol

Not applicable

Data, code and other materials

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as it is a protocol, so no datasets were generated or analysed.

Disclosure of artificial intelligence use

We did not use AI systems or tools for any protocol processes.

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Table 1: Outcome definitions

Intraoperative events/ complications	Total operative time	Skin incision to skin closure, or as reported by the authors
	Intra-operative pain	Acute and intense pain during caesarean section, or as reported by the authors
	Intra-operative nausea or vomiting	Nausea or vomiting during caesarean section, or as reported by the authors
Postoperative recovery before discharge	Length of hospital stay	Time from post-op to discharge, or as reported by the authors
	Post-operative pain	Acute and intense pain 2-5 days after caesarean section, or as reported by the authors
	Post-operative nausea or vomiting	Nausea or vomiting from post-op to discharge, or as reported by the authors
	Time to bowel movement	Time from post-op to the first bowel movement, or as reported by the authors
Infectious morbidity	Surgical site infection	Microbiologically confirmed infection of the operative site up to six weeks postpartum, or as reported by the authors
	Endometritis	Microbiologically confirmed infection of the lining of the uterus up to six weeks postpartum, or as reported by the authors
	Sepsis	Microbiologically confirmed infection of the bloodstream up to six weeks postpartum, or as reported by the authors
	Febrile morbidity	Temperature of 38 degrees Celsius or more, at least on one occasion, up to six weeks postpartum, or as reported by the authors
	Infectious morbidity	Composite outcome of surgical site infection, endometritis, sepsis, and febrile morbidity
Hemorrhagic morbidity	Blood loss	Mean blood loss in mL intraoperative to 3 days, or as reported by the authors
	Post-partum haemorrhage (PPH)	(independent of the amount of blood loss) intraoperative to 3 days, or as reported by the authors
	Blood transfusion	Need for blood transfusion intraoperative to 3 days, or as reported by the authors
	Need for additional uterotonics	Including oxytocin, misoprostol, ergometrine, carbetocin, or others reported by authors, intraoperative to 3 days, or as reported by authors
Severe maternal morbidity	Maternal death	Intraoperative to 3 days, or as reported by the authors
	Severe morbidity	Maternal deaths or severe morbidity events, including major surgery (laparotomy, uterine artery ligation, internal iliac artery ligation, B-Lynch suture, hysterectomy), admission to the intensive care unit (ICU), or vital organ failure (temporary or permanent), intraoperative to 3 days or as reported by authors
Long-term effects	Dysmenorrhea	New onset of severe, painful menstrual cramps in the lower abdomen more than 6 months postpartum, or as reported by the authors
	Chronic pelvic pain	Severe pain more than 6 months postpartum, or as reported by the authors
Effects on subsequent pregnancy/birth	Uterine scar defect (Niche)	A wedge-shaped pouch at the site of cesarean section incision on imaging at subsequent pregnancy/birth, or as reported by the authors
	Abdominal adhesions	Bands of scar tissue causing organs to stick together, as seen on imaging or visualisation, at subsequent pregnancy/birth, or as reported by the authors
	Placental anomalies	Including placenta previa and placenta accreta, at subsequent pregnancy/birth, or as reported by the authors
	Uterine rupture	at subsequent pregnancy/birth, or as reported by the authors
	Uterine scar dehiscence	at subsequent pregnancy/birth, or as reported by the authors

Table 2: Domains and check of the INSPECT-SR tool

DOMAIN	Response
1. Inspecting post-publication notices	
1.1. Does the study have an associated retraction?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
1.2. Does the study have an associated expression of concern or other relevant post publication notice?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
1.3. Do other studies by the research team highlight causes for concern (associated retractions, expressions of concern, relevant post-publication notices?)	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
Overall domain judgement	No concerns, some concerns, serious concerns
2. Inspecting conduct, governance, and transparency	
2.1. Are there concerns relating to ethical approval?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
2.2. Are there concerns relating to the timing or absence of study registration?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
2.3. Are there important inconsistencies between the publication and the registration documents?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
2.4. Is the recruitment of participants implausible?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
2.5. Are the reported methods implausible considering the reported resources?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
Overall domain judgement	No concerns, some concerns, serious concerns
3. Inspecting text and figures	
3.1. Are there concerns relating to duplicated content, such as text or tables, or text that is incompatible with the study?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
3.2. Is there evidence of manipulation or duplication of figures?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
Overall domain judgement	No concerns, some concerns, serious concerns
4. Inspecting results in the study	
4.1. Are there any unexplained discrepancies between reported data and participant eligibility criteria?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.2. Are numbers of participants allocated to each group implausible given the allocation method?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.3. Are any baseline data implausible?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.4. Are there any discrepancies between results reported in figures, tables, and text?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.5. Are the numbers of participants lost to follow-up implausible?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.6. Are there any unexplained inconsistencies in the numbers of participants?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.7. Are any outcome data, including estimated treatment effects, implausible?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.8. Are the means and variances of integer data impossible?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.9. Are there errors in statistical results?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.10. Are any other contradictions implied by the data?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
4.11. Are there inconsistencies in descriptions of methods and results across publications describing the study?	Yes, No, Unclear or Not applicable
Overall domain judgement	No concerns, some concerns, serious concerns

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Figures

Figure 1

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Supplementary material

Search strategies

Preliminary Medline search strategy

- 1 exp Cesarean Section/ (57390)
- 2 Cesarean*.mp. (84516)
- 3 Caesarean*.mp. (27806)
- 4 c-section*.mp. (2530)
- 5 ((abdominal or surgical) adj1 deliver*).tw. (1106)
- 6 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 (98200)
- 7 Uterus/ (65309)
- 8 Wound Closure Techniques/ or Suture Techniques/ or Sutures/ (62312)
- 9 ((Uterine or uterus) and (closure or close* or repair or sutur* or stitch*)).mp. (15960)
- 10 ((Uterine or uterus) and ("surg* technique*" or exteriori#ation)).mp. (1896)
- 11 (Extra-abdominal or intra-abdominal or "single layer" or "two layers").mp. (54531)
- 12 ((Interrupted or continuous or locked or unlocked) adj6 (sudur* or stitch*)).mp. (4872)
- 13 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 (195583)
- 14 6 and 13 (5339)
- 15 exp randomized controlled trial/ (655004)
- 16 controlled clinical trial.pt. (95754)
- 17 randomized.ab. (728655)
- 18 placebo.ab. (265928)
- 19 drug therapy.fs. (2894829)
- 20 randomly.ab. (478684)
- 21 trial.ab. (797549)
- 22 groups.ab. (2978674)
- 23 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 (6530851)
- 24 exp animals/ not humans.sh. (5417294)
- 25 23 not 24 (5733149)
- 26 14 and 25 (1120)